

Assembling a Cohort of Hyposmic Participants for Therapeutic Studies Aimed at Parkinson's Disease (PD) Prevention

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INTRODUCTION

The Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) is a longitudinal, observational study launched by The Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF) in 2010 to identify biomarkers of PD toward accelerating therapeutic development. PPMI has recently focused on enrolling individuals with hyposmia, a predictive marker of PD. Amassing a cohort of individuals with hyposmia to later invite them to participate in clinical trials for PD prevention is described here.

METHODS

Widespread recruitment efforts and a staged-screening paradigm were used to identify participants. Utilizing broad media/social media outreach, email campaigns, and paid partnerships, candidates over age 60 were sent to a website managed by a study partner, who conducted centralized initial remote screening of the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) smell test. Participants whose UPSIT results showed olfactory loss were invited to go to a PPMI study site for a DaTscan to further assess study eligibility. PPMI study team worked with clinical sites ensuring capacity and efficient scheduling for imaging and enrollment visits.

RESULTS

As of early 2024 over 79,800 individuals consented to take a smell test. Over 57,700 participants answered additional screening questions and were sent a smell test. More than 38,000 UPSITs were completed; 6,649 hyposmic individuals were identified and 2,833 agreed to undergo a DaTscan; 1,720 completed a DaTscan; 1,120 were invited to join the longitudinal PPMI study; 731 hyposmic participants have so far enrolled in the clinical study through these recruitment efforts. Paid and earned media efforts led to the highest volume of consents for the smell test of all recruitment strategies utilized.

Recruitment --> Screening --> Enrollment

Recruitment Methods

Proportion of total consented participants recruited from:

DISCUSSION

Remaining agile with recruitment methods and being ready to adjust in real time is key to achieving recruiting goals. Effective participant engagement at every step is also crucial. A centralized screening team helps to reduce site burden. Thoughtful site selection and support is key to ensuring efficient enrollment of participants in longitudinal trials.

CONCLUSION

Utilizing comprehensive centralized recruitment and screening strategies, PPMI successfully recruited hyposmic individuals for future clinical trials targeting PD prevention. Educating participants on screening rationale and study activities at each step has been critical to converting interested candidates to enrolled participants. These learnings may allow others in the field of PD research to recruit, screen and enroll hyposmic individuals more effectively.

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